

Full Length Article

Radiation-resistant thin LGADs for enhanced 4D tracking

A.R. Altamura^{a,b}, R.S. White^b, M. Ferrero^b, L. Anderlini^c, R. Arcidiacono^{b,d},
G. Borghi^e, M. Boscardin^e, N. Cartiglia^b, M. Centis Vignali^e, T. Croci^f, F. Davolio^e,
M. Durando^a, A. Fondacci^{f,g}, S. Galletto^a, L. Lanteri^{a,b}, L. Menzio^b, A. Morozzi^f,
D. Passeri^{f,g}, N. Pastrone^b, F. Siviero^d, F. Moscatelli^{f,h}, G. Paternoster^e, V. Sola^{a,b}

^a Università di Torino, via P. Giuria 1, 10125 Torino, Italy

^b INFN, Sezione di Torino, via P. Giuria 1, 10125 Torino, Italy

^c INFN, Sezione di Firenze, Largo Enrico Fermi 1, 50125 Firenze, Italy

^d Università degli Studi del Piemonte Orientale, largo G. Donegani 2/3, 28100 Novara, Italy

^e Fondazione Bruno Kessler, via Sommarive 18, 38123 Povo (TN), Italy

^f Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare, Sezione di Perugia, via A. Pascoli 23c, 06123 Perugia, Italy

^g Università degli Studi di Perugia, via G. Duranti 93, 06125 Perugia, Italy

^h CNR-IOM, Sede secondaria di Perugia, via A. Pascoli 23c, 06123 Perugia, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Low-Gain Avalanche Diodes
Radiation tolerance
Timing resolution

ABSTRACT

This contribution presents the results of an R&D study on the EXFLU1 batch, a novel concept of thin Low Gain Avalanche Diodes (LGADs) designed to achieve improved timing resolution and radiation tolerance up to $25 \times 10^{14} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}\text{cm}^{-2}$. Sensors with different thicknesses (15, 20, 30, and 45 μm) have been explored. New designs for the gain layer and guard ring structure have been investigated, along with two different doping activation methods. The sensors have been irradiated up to $25 \times 10^{14} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}\text{cm}^{-2}$ and characterised in terms of current, capacitance, and gain to assess their radiation tolerance. Finally, 30 μm LGADs were tested in a 4 GeV electron beam to evaluate their timing resolution.

1. Introduction

Next-generation high-energy particle colliders, designed for fundamental physics research, will require ultra-precise tracking in both space and time. In these environments, tracking detectors are expected to survive extreme radiation levels, requiring extensive R&D to increase their radiation tolerance and extend operational limits as far as possible.

The key advantage of LGADs lies in their internal avalanche multiplication process, which enables high-precision time tracking with a good timing resolution (~ 30 ps), maintaining performance up to fluences of $25 \times 10^{14} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}\text{cm}^{-2}$, which represents the current limit to their radiation tolerance [1]. The gain layer is obtained by implanting a thin p^+ region with an acceptor concentration of $\sim 10^{16}\text{--}10^{17} \text{ atoms cm}^{-3}$ beneath the n^{++} electrode. However, this structure suffers from partial deactivation of these acceptors at fluences $\sim 10^{16} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}\text{cm}^{-2}$, significantly impacting gain and timing performance. The main damage mechanism responsible for gain deactivation is known as *acceptor removal* [2], which consists of electronic deactivation of boron in the gain implant

according to the formula:

$$p^+(\Phi) = p_0^+ e^{-c_A \Phi} \quad (1)$$

where p_0^+ is the initial acceptor density, Φ is the fluence and c_A is the *acceptor removal coefficient* that will be investigated in the following as the main figure of merit for the study of the radiation tolerance in LGADs.

2. The EXFLU1 batch

The primary goals for the EXFLU1 batch are to enhance timing resolution and improve radiation tolerance, pushing the limits of current detector technology. The first batch was designed in collaboration with Perugia group, produced by FBK in 2023, and subsequently characterised in Torino. Later, sensors were irradiated at the TRIGA Mark II research nuclear reactor at the Jozef Stefan Institute (JSI) under different fluences ($4\text{--}8\text{--}15\text{--}25 \times 10^{14} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}\text{cm}^{-2}$) and annealed at 60 °C for 80 min.

* Corresponding author at: Università di Torino, via P. Giuria 1, 10125 Torino, Italy.
E-mail address: annarita.altamura@unito.it (A.R. Altamura).

Table 1
Specifications of the EXFLU1 LGADs, where carbon is co-implanted with boron in the gain layer (Carbon dose = 1).

Wafer	Thickness [μm]	p^+ dose	Diffusion	Bulk
1	45	1.14	CBL	very high ρ
5	30	1.12	CBL	high ρ
16	20	0.80	CHBL	high ρ
17	20	0.96	CBL	high ρ
18	15	0.94	CBL	high ρ

This batch is characterised by an optimised gain layer and guard ring design. Various thin substrates (15, 20, 30 and 45 μm) have been investigated, along with a comparative analysis of two distinct doping activation strategies at a fixed thickness: Carbon Boron Low (CBL) and Carbon High Boron Low (CHBL) [3], as visible in Table 1. In the CBL scheme, both carbon and boron are activated simultaneously under a low heat load. Conversely, in the CHBL scheme, carbon is activated at a higher temperature prior to boron, which undergoes activation at a lower temperature.

The batch specifications are shown in Table 1. The doping concentration in the gain layer was calibrated based on the different sensors thickness and their bulk resistivity, in order to achieve a consistent working point across all samples. The 45 μm wafer exhibited a phenomenon that can be attributed to a doping inversion in pre-irradiation conditions, likely due to the significantly high resistivity of the bulk material. Consequently, $C-V$ results associated with this wafer in pre-irradiation conditions will not be presented in the following discussion. Wafers 16 and 17 have the same thickness but differ in the doping diffusion mode, requiring precise tuning of the p^+ dose. In particular, wafer 17 needs a higher p^+ dose due to the reduced activation of dopants resulting from the CBL activation process [3].

3. Characterisation

Sensor characterisation includes both static and transient measurements. The static characterisation helps evaluate the overall quality of the fabrication process and determine critical parameters such as the gain layer and bulk depletion voltages, V_{GL} and V_{FD} respectively, by analysing the current I and capacitance C as a function of the applied reverse bias V . The evolution of V_{GL} and V_{FD} under irradiation provide a useful measurement of the sensor's radiation tolerance.

The transient characterisation examines the response of the sensor to external stimuli, simulating conditions similar to those experienced when the sensor is hit by a particle. The gain can be obtained from such measurements, providing insights into the amount of damage the gain layer undergoes under irradiation, as well as information on the sensor's operational status after exposure to a specific fluence. Irradiated sensors were additionally exposed to a 4 GeV electron beam at DESY, in order to study their timing performance.

3.1. Static characterisation

$I-V$ and $C-V$ measurements are performed using an MPI TS200-SE probe station, where the sensor is placed on a temperature-controlled chuck, and electrical connections are made via probes contacting the metal pads on the sensor surface [3]. The $I-V$ scan has been performed in -2 V bias intervals up to the breakdown voltage at different temperatures: $+20$ °C for un-irradiated and -20 °C for irradiated sensors. The $I-V$ characteristics for un-irradiated sensors are presented for each thickness in Fig. 1. All sensors exhibit similar operating points, with V_{GL} values confined within a narrow range and V_{FD} values falling within a limited interval between 100 and 200 V, as determined by the gain layer design. Furthermore, the presence of carbon in the gain

Fig. 1. $I-V$ curves of un-irradiated sensors performed at $+20$ °C.

Fig. 2. $C^{-2}-V$ at different fluences for wafer 18 (15 μm) at $+20$ °C, with a zoom view of the region corresponding to the depletion voltage of the gain layer to highlight the evolution of V_{GL} due to irradiation.

implant results in a detectable dark current even before reaching the V_{GL} value.

The $C-V$ measurements were performed at $+20$ °C within a 1–2 kHz frequency range, selected based on preliminary capacitance versus frequency ($C-f$) measurements performed on each sensor. The capacitance behaviour as a function of reverse bias for different fluence levels for wafer 18 (15 μm) is presented in Fig. 2. Due to its sharper curve, C^{-2} is often plotted to provide a clearer indication of depletion points. A comparison between un-irradiated and irradiated sensors clearly indicates degradation in both the gain layer and the bulk, due to the acceptor removal mechanism. This effect primarily occurs in the gain layer, but is also observed in the bulk as a consequence of its high doping concentration. In Fig. 2, a zoom view of the depletion voltage region of the gain layer is highlighted. A slight shift of V_{GL} by approximately 5 V is observed, indicating the impact of the radiation damage on the gain layer.

V_{GL} values are extracted from capacitance measurements by using different methods. In this production, four methods are used and compared [4]:

- *First derivative*: the value of V_{GL} is identified as the voltage at which the first derivative of C^{-2} reaches its maximum
- *Linear fit*: a linear fit is applied to the flat region of the curve before the sharp increase, and another is applied to the region of rising C^{-2} . V_{GL} is determined as the voltage at which these two fitted lines intersect
- *Fixed capacitance*: using as a threshold a fixed C^{-2} , the V_{GL} value is extracted as the corresponding bias voltage where the curve intersects the threshold
- R_p : if considering the sensor as modelled by a C_p-R_p equivalent circuit, the R_p curve as a function of the bias exhibits a cusp at the depletion voltage of the gain layer

Fig. 3. V_{GL} as a function of the fluence for all the wafers under test estimated by using the R_p method. No V_{GL} data are available for wafer 1 LGAD (45 μm) in pre-irradiation conditions.

Table 2

c_A values [$\times 10^{-16}$ $\text{n}_{\text{eq}}\text{cm}^{-2}$] extracted from all the methods under consideration for each wafer, with a final value calculated as the mean of the four methods.

Wafer	1 st der	Linear fit	Fixed C	R_p	Mean
1	0.95	1.04	–	1.08	1.02 ± 0.07
5	1.36	1.20	1.12	1.21	1.22 ± 0.10
16	2.07	2.09	2.07	2.21	2.11 ± 0.07
17	1.24	1.21	1.37	1.34	1.29 ± 0.08
18	1.13	1.06	1.35	1.52	1.27 ± 0.21

By using the linear dependence of V_{GL} on the doping concentration p^+ , the exponential relationship in Eq. (1) remains valid for V_{GL} , enabling the extraction of the acceptor removal coefficient c_A from an exponential fit of the V_{GL} curves as a function of the fluence, as shown in Fig. 3 using the R_p method.

The c_A values have been extracted by fitting the V_{GL} values from all four methods, with a mean value of all methods used as the final value, as visible in Table 2. No data are available for the wafer 1 using the fixed capacitance method. A comparison between wafer 16 (CHBL) and wafer 17 (CBL) at the same thickness reveals that CBL activation results in better radiation tolerance. Overall, the EXFLU1 batch provides the best c_A value among all the FBK LGAD technologies produced to date.

3.2. Transient characterisation

Sensor charge collection properties have been analysed using a Transient Current Technique (TCT), consisting of a pulsed laser light directed onto structures equipped with an LGAD and a PIN, generating electron–hole pairs within the active region while an external bias voltage is applied. The sensors were maintained at -13 °C, and a picosecond IR laser at wavelength of 1064 nm was used to release charge equivalent to ~ 4 MIPs [5]. This specific intensity was chosen to provide an enhanced signal for more accurate measurements while preventing excessive charge release that could induce shielding effects. The output signal, measured for increasing bias, was amplified by a 40 dB, 2 GHz Cividec amplifier operating in current mode, and recorded by an oscilloscope triggered on the laser pulse signal.

By exploiting the fact that the area of the signal is proportional to the collected charge, the gain is determined by comparing the effective signal area of the LGAD (after baseline subtraction) to that of the corresponding PIN diode of the same design with no gain implant. Fig. 4 presents the results of the gain measurements on the wafer 5 sensor (30 μm) for all the fluences under test, showing that even after irradiation up to 25×10^{14} $\text{n}_{\text{eq}}\text{cm}^{-2}$, the sensor still operates with a gain of ~ 10 , well before reaching the Single Event Burnout (SEB) of $\sim E_{\text{field}} \geq 14$ V/ μm ($V_{\text{SEB}} = 420$ V) for this sensor thickness [6].

Fig. 4. Gain of wafer 5 LGAD (30 μm) as a function of the reverse bias for all the fluences under investigation.

Fig. 5. Timing resolution as a function of the collected charge for the wafer 5 (30 μm) sensor at all the fluences under test. The unirradiated sensor was measured at $+20$ °C, while the irradiated sensors were tested in a temperature range from -50 °C to -35 °C.

3.3. Timing resolution

One of the primary objectives of the R&D presented in this work is to assess the timing resolution of thin LGADs when exposed to radiation up to a fluence of 25×10^{14} $\text{n}_{\text{eq}}\text{cm}^{-2}$. For this purpose, EXFLU1 sensors were tested using a 4 GeV electron beam at DESY in December 2024 [7]. The sensors were mounted on a single-channel Santa Cruz Board for the initial amplification stage and subsequently connected to a 20 dB, 2 GHz Cividec amplifier. The signals were recorded using an 8-channel Lecroy oscilloscope (2 GHz bandwidth, 10 GSa/s sampling rate). The experimental setup included a 13 mm^2 , 45 μm thick LGAD as a trigger and a Microchannel Plate (MCP) as a precise time reference. The irradiated sensors were cooled using dry ice and tested within a temperature range between -50 °C and -35 °C, monitored via an Arduino-based system.

The timing resolution was estimated using the following equation:

$$\sigma_t(DUT) = \sqrt{\sigma_t^2(MCP; DUT) - \sigma_t^2(MCP)} \quad (2)$$

assuming an intrinsic MCP timing resolution $\sigma_t(MCP)$ of 5 ps.

The wafer 5 (30 μm) timing resolution is presented in Fig. 5 as a function of the collected charge for all tested fluences. An excellent timing performance is demonstrated, achieving 22 ps for the unirradiated sensor. For the irradiated sensors, an even better timing resolution is maintained for collected charges around 3–4 fC, extending up to 9 fC, before the onset of SEB. It is worth mentioning that the temperature variations during data taking, which influence the bias voltage required to collect a given charge [3], do not affect the measurements.

4. Conclusion

An R&D program has been carried out to develop thin LGADs with the primary objectives of enhancing the radiation tolerance and timing resolution of current LGAD technologies. For this purpose, the EXFLU1 batch was released by FBK in 2023, including improvements in gain layer and guard ring design, by exploring thin substrates (ranging from 15 to 45 μm). Variations in p^+ doping density and bulk resistivity were also introduced. Two different doping implantation strategies were also explored: CBL, where carbon and boron are implanted and activated simultaneously, and CHBL, where carbon is implanted and activated before boron. The sensors were irradiated with neutrons at JSI over a fluence range up to $25 \times 10^{14} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

Sensors were then characterised through static and transient measurements to evaluate their radiation tolerance. The $I - V$ characteristics revealed that the sensors exhibit similar working points in terms of breakdown voltage and gain layer depletion voltage. As expected from theoretical predictions, irradiation resulted in a gain degradation and an increase in dark current. From $C - V$ measurements the V_{GL} values were extracted using four different methods, and subsequently fitted with an exponential function to determine the acceptor removal coefficient c_A . The final value was obtained by averaging the results from the four methods, providing the best c_A values ever recorded in FBK productions to date. From transient characterisation the gain evolution was measured, showing a general decrease with irradiation. However, the sensors remained operational with a gain of ~ 10 up to a fluence of $25 \times 10^{14} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, before reaching the SEB limit.

Subsequently, sensors were tested in a 4 GeV beam at DESY to assess their timing resolution where excellent results were observed, reaching 22 ps for the unirradiated sensor. Even in the irradiated sensors, a timing resolution of 22 ps was achieved at a collected charge of 3–4 fC, with further improvement at higher charges up to 9 fC.

Overall, the successful R&D on thin LGADs produced a significant improvement in timing resolution and radiation tolerance up to $25 \times 10^{14} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, marking a notable step forward in the development of future sensors for 4D-tracking.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreements Nos 101004761 (AIDAInnova) and 101057511 (EURO-LABS), the European Union – Next Generation EU, Mission 4 Component 1 CUP D53D23002870001 (ComonSens), and the INFN CSN5 through the 'eXFlu' research project. Part of the measurements leading to these results have been performed at the Test Beam Facility at DESY Hamburg (Germany), a member of the Helmholtz Association (HGF).

References

- [1] R.S. White, et al., Characterisation of the FBK EXFLU1 thin sensors with gain in a high fluence environment, Nucl. Instrum. Methods A 1068 (2024) 169798, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2024.169798>.
- [2] M. Moll, Acceptor removal — Displacement damage effects involving the shallow acceptor doping of p-type silicon devices, PoS Vertex2019 (2020) 027, <http://dx.doi.org/10.22323/1.373.0027>.
- [3] M. Ferrero, R. Arcidiacono, M. Mandurrino, V. Sola, N. Cartiglia, An introduction to ultra-fast silicon detectors: Design, tests, and performances, 2021, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1201/9781003131946>.
- [4] M. Ferrero, et al., Radiation resistant LGAD design, Nucl. Instrum. Methods A 919 (2019) 16–26, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2018.11.121>.
- [5] S. Meroli, D. Passeri, L. Servoli, Energy loss measurement for charged particles in very thin silicon layers, J. Instrum. 6 (06) (2011) P06013, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/6/06/P06013>.
- [6] M. Ferrero, et al., Single event burnout in thin silicon sensors, in: 43rd RD50 Workshop, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland, 2023, URL <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1334364/contributions/5672087/>.
- [7] M. Ferrero, et al., Timing resolution of thin LGAD sensors for high radiation environments, in: TREDI, 2025, URL <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1455346/contributions/6323206/>.